

6G SNS

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D3.2 HARDWARE PLATFORM SUPPORT FOR CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

CONFIDENTIAL6G has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101096435

PROJECT INFORMATION

Call	HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022
Type of Action	HORIZON-JU-RIA HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
Project start date	01/01/2023
Duration	36 months
GA No	101096435

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Deliverable WP:	WP3
Deliverable Task:	Task T3.2
Deliverable Identifier:	CONFIDENTIAL6G_D3.2
Deliverable Title:	HARDWARE PLATFORM SUPPORT FOR CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING
Editor(s):	UVC
Author(s):	Danko Miladinović (UVC), Markku Kylänpää (VTT)
Reviewer(s):	Dimitrios Schoinianakis (NOK), Fabian Schmid (TUG)
Contractual Date of Delivery:	31/12/2024
Submission Date:	20/12/2024
Dissemination Level:	PU
Status:	Final
Version:	1.0
File Name:	CONFIDENTIAL6G_D3.2_Hardware_Platform_Support_for_Confidential_Computing_v1.0.docx

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DOCUMENT LOG

VERSION	DATE	DESCRIPTION OF CHANGE
1.0	20/12/2024	Final version, submitted to EC through SyGMa

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
ACM	Authenticated Code Modules (Intel)
AMD	Advanced Micro Devices
AMD-SP	AMD Secure Processor (also known as ASP or PSP)
AMX	Advanced Matrix Extensions (Intel)
API	Application Programming Interface
ARM	Advanced RISC Machines
ASF	Apache Software Foundation
ASIC	Application-Specific Integrated Circuit
ASP	AMD Secure Processor (also known as PSP or AMD-SP)
CBOR	Concise Binary Object Representation
CCA	Confidential Compute Architecture (ARM)
CIA	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability
CKKS	Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song
CoVE	Confidential VM Environment (RISC-V)
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
DICE	Device Identifier Composition Engine (TCG)
DMTF	Distributed Management Task Force
EAR	EAT Attestation Results
EAT	Entity Attestation Token
EOS	Enclave OS
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FHE	Fully Homomorphic Encryption
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
gRPC	Open-source universal RPC framework
HEXL	Homomorphic Encryption Acceleration Library
IDE	Integrity and Data Encryption

IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KDS	Key Distribution System (AMD)
KVM	Kernel-based Virtual Machine
MA	Migration Agent (AMD)
ME	Management Engine (Intel)
MEC	Memory Encryption Context (ARM)
MK	Master Key pair
MKTME	Multi-key Total Memory Encryption (Intel)
MRTD	Measurement of Trust Domain (Intel)
MTT	Memory Tracking Table (RISC-V)
NRAS	Nvidia Remote Attestation Service
NTT	Number Theoretic Transform
OCSP	Online Certificate Service Protocol
OS	Operating System
PCI	Peripheral Component Interconnect
PCI-SIG	PCI Special Interest Group
PCK	Provisioning Certification Key (Intel)
PCS	Provisioning Certification Service (Intel)
PMP	Physical Memory Protection (RISC-V)
PSA	Platform Security Architecture (ARM)
PSP	Platform Security Processor (AMD) (a.k.a. ASP or AMD-SP)
QE	Quoting Enclave (Intel SGX)
RATS	Remote Attestation Procedures (IETF)
REE	Rich OS Execution Environment
RISC	Reduced Instruction Set Computer
RISC-V	RISC 5 (the fifth generation)
RME	Realm Management Extensions (ARM)
RMI	Realm Management Interface (ARM)
RMM	Realm Management Monitor (ARM)
RPC	Remote Procedure Call

RSI	Real Service Interface (ARM)
RTMR	Runtime Measurement Registers (Intel)
SA	Security Agent
SBI	Supervisor Binary Interface (RISC-V)
SDK	Software Development Kit
SEAM	SEcure Arbitration Mode (Intel)
SEV	Secure Encrypted Virtualization (AMD)
SEV-ES	SEV-Encrypted State (AMD)
SEV-SNP	SEV-Secure Nested Paging (AMD)
SEV-TIO	SEV Trusted I/O (AMD)
SGX	Software Guard Extensions (Intel)
SIMD	Single Instruction/Multiple Data
SME	Secure Memory Encryption (AMD)
SoC	System on a Chip
SPDM	Security Protocol and Data Model
SPM	Secure Partition Manager (ARM)
TA	Trusted Application
TCB	Trusted Computing Base
TCG	Trusted Computing Group
TDISP	TEE Device Interface Security Protocol
TDX	Trust Domain Extensions (Intel)
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TME	Total Memory Encryption (Intel)
TOS	Trusted OS
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
TSM	TEE Security Manager (RISC-V)
TSME	Transparent SME (AMD)
TVM	TEE Virtual Machine (RISC-V CoVE)
UML	Unified Modeling Language
VCEK	Versioned Chip-Endorsement Key (Attestation Key)(AMD)

VM	Virtual Machine
VMM	Virtual Machine Monitor (also known as a hypervisor)
VMX	Virtual Machine Extensions
VT	Virtualization Technology (Intel)
vTPM	Virtual TPM
WASI	WebAssembly System Interface
WASM	WebAssembly Runtime

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports the work done in the CONFIDENTIAL6G project regarding hardware platforms for confidential computing. It describes a solution for a unified software interface of trusted execution environments (TEEs) and the current state of technology of TEEs. Also, it describes the related work for a unified software interface.

The document is first analysing four different TEE platforms (AMD SEV-SNP, Intel TDX, ARM CCA, and RISC-V CoVE). These platforms can be used to run confidential virtual machines that can be used with unmodified confidential workloads typically as a cloud service. The ability to be able to use unmodified workloads simplifies development of applications requiring confidential computing protection. Earlier approaches (e.g., Intel SGX enclaves) were using resource constrained environment for a single computing task requiring confidentiality protection requiring developers to modify their applications.

Computing tasks, e.g., AI/ML, might require the use of accelerators, like GPUs, to speed-up computing. However, this could expose confidential data to eavesdroppers.

Cloud service providers will support at least AMD and Intel TEE platforms. Soon there can be other alternatives, like ARM and RISC-V based TEE platforms. Users might want to use a toolkit that could utilize multiple platforms hiding platform details from end-users. There are attempts to build such toolkits and main alternatives are presented in this document.

CONFIDENTIAL6G is developing a toolkit that could support multiple TEE platforms. The prototype is currently mainly supporting AMD SEV-SNP platform. The toolkit is utilizing Go programming language and can be ported to support multiple TEE platforms.

1 INTRODUCTION

Confidential computing deals with the protection of data in use. Confidential computing systems aim to provide confidentiality for data processing. Integrity verification is also needed to be able to detect unauthorized modifications. These requirements can be met by providing hardware-based isolated execution environments known as Trusted Execution Environment (TEE).

1.1 SCOPE

This document describes hardware platform support for confidential computing. Confidential computing related threats and adversaries are analysed and linked to requirements. The document is also describing major confidential computing hardware platforms and analysing their main features. There are also many frameworks and tools that have been developed to hide implementation details and to give higher-level abstractions for developers. The document provides an overview of these tools and frameworks. Remote attestation and hardware acceleration issues are also covered. The document also presents an architecture for confidential computing. The document also includes design and analysis of prototyped platforms and covers interface descriptions for abstract TEE access as well as implementation experiences related to Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) acceleration.

1.2 DOCUMENT ORGANIZATION

The document is organized as follows. In section 2 we are covering adversary and threat model for confidential computing platforms utilizing also CONFIDENTIAL6G confidential computing requirements analysis document D3.1 [1]. Section 3 describes four major hardware platforms for computing. Intel, AMD, ARM, and RISC-V confidential computing hardware platforms are described. Tools and frameworks for confidential computing are described in section 4. Attestation mechanism is a corner stone in confidential computing, and it is described in section 5. Section 6 is discussing various accelerators and their role in confidential computing. High-level architecture is described in section 7. Concluding remarks are presented in section 8.

2 ADVERSARY AND THREAT MODEL

Information security is typically focused on protection of confidentiality, integrity, and availability (also known as CIA triad). Our high-level security objective is to provide confidentiality and integrity protection for confidential virtual machines. Availability has smaller priority. Because our architecture intends to support multiple platforms (e.g., AMD SEV-SNP, Intel TDX, ARM CCA, and RISC-V CoVE), it is crucial to study what kind of threat models and assumptions these platforms are using and to compare their threat models. Platform specific threat models are presented in the next section together with platform descriptions.

2.1 CONFIDENTIALITY

Confidential computing systems are typically implemented as a cloud service. There is only limited physical security as cloud provider always has physical access to their own system. Malicious cloud provider could access all data and software in their system. Confidential computing platforms are tackling this by using trust relationships with hardware providers, utilizing TEEs, and using encryption. Although a cloud provider is able to control many system components, the system is built in such a way that confidentiality is preserved.

Even though security architecture seems to be able to mitigate typical confidentiality threats, there are still many ways to attack, and platform-specific threat models may not cover all possible attacks. Side-channel threats are typically platform dependent and new kind of side-channels are sometimes found (e.g., speculative execution-based attacks). Another class of attacks that is often omitted is low-level hardware attacks, like fault injections or memory rollback. Asymmetric cryptography that is used in these systems is not yet post-quantum safe.

2.2 INTEGRITY

Although adversaries may not be able to access plain text material, it is often still possible to make unauthorized modifications to encrypted files that are accessible for untrusted components. In addition to brute force attacks, there can be attempts to replace encrypted components with older versions that are known to be vulnerable and utilize attacks that are fixed in new versions.

2.3 AVAILABILITY

Confidential computing platforms are typically designed to co-exist with more generic computing environments and to share system components with them. For example, in many virtual machine-based systems, the hypervisor is considered to be untrusted. The system is still able to protect the confidentiality and integrity of the virtual machines. However, availability may be affected if a malicious hypervisor denies execution and other system services from confidential virtual machines.

Cloud-based systems also have many infrastructure, capacity, and networking-related availability threats. Cloud providers are trying to mitigate these threats. For example, migration support for virtual machines to survive planned maintenance breaks can be provided. Some confidential computing platforms support migration and live migration support also for confidential virtual machines.

2.4 TEE-RELATED THREATS

Threats related to TEE have also been discussed in the requirements document [1]. The analysis gave examples of threats based on STRIDE methodology and mitigation mechanisms. Further analysis of TEE-related threats can be found in [2].

3 HARDWARE PLATFORMS

In this section, we describe potential hardware platforms for confidential computing. The platforms typically use virtualization approaches, allowing the setup of confidential virtual machines and running unmodified applications with confidentiality and integrity protection for data in use. Our analysis is focused on four hardware platforms. There are more, but in this deliverable, we are covering only these four platforms: Intel TDX, AMD SEV-SNP, ARM CCA, and RISC-V CoVE. All these platforms provide an architecture that allows the creation of isolated execution environments and to provide confidentiality and integrity protection. There is a brief description followed by platform-specific threat model discussion and a summary table of features for each platform.

3.1 INTEL TDX

Intel Trust Domain Extensions (TDX) is a recent addition to confidential computing hardware platforms that are available in new Intel Xeon processors [3], [4]. TDX is a successor to Intel SGX borrowing features from AMD SEV-SNP. However, TDX also includes SGX components.

3.1.1 DESCRIPTION

TDX is utilizing multiple Intel technologies to build a platform for confidential computing. The following building blocks are used:

- **Virtualization Technology (VT)** – Intel’s full virtualization platform [5] that is commonly used to run guest operating systems controlled by a special instruction set called Virtual Machine Extensions (VMX). VT can also provide isolation between virtual machines, but the VT hypervisor is then part of a trusted computing base.
- **Multi-key Total Memory Encryption (MKTME)** – MKTME [6] is used to encrypt main memory supporting multiple keys and enabling page-level granularity for encryption.
- **Software Guard Extensions (SGX)** – SGX is aimed to provide confidentiality and integrity guarantees for a secure enclave even when all the privileged software components (e.g., kernel, hypervisor) are non-trusted [7]. TDX is using SGX attestation functionality.
- **Data Center Attestation Primitives (DCAP)** – DCAP (a part of SGX) is also used to support attestation in TDX [8].
- **TDX Module** – This specification contains the main logic of Intel TDX [9].

Intel TDX can also provide access to trusted devices by utilizing TEE Device Interface Security Protocol (TDISP) specified by PCI-SIG [10]. Using these building blocks Intel TDX can provide confidential virtual machines called Intel TDX Trust Domains. High-level architecture is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Intel TDX Architectural Overview

Intel has the Provisioning Certification Service (PCS) that can be used to verify the authenticity of the platform. The service provides Provisioning Certification Key (PCK) certificates for devices and certificate revocation lists of these certificates. Intel TDX remote attestation flow is presented in Figure 2. A Remote third party can send an attestation request with a random nonce to an attestation agent that is located inside the Intel TDX Trust Domain. Intel TDX also includes an architecture for taking measurements that resembles the Trusted Platform Module (TPM). For each Trust Domain, there are build-time and runtime registers that are used to measure execution. The Build-time register is called Measurement of Trust Domain (MRTD), and it is used to measure events when the Trust Domain is created. Another set of registers is called Runtime Measurement Registers (RTMRs) and these registers are used to measure execution inside the Trust Domain. These registers are updated using a TPM-like extend operation using SHA-384 cryptographic hash algorithm. These

register values are embedded in the Intel TDX attestation report provided by Quoting Enclave component.

Figure 2. Intel TDX remote attestation flow

3.1.2 THREAT MODEL

Intel TDX is calling confidential virtual machines Trust Domains. A high-level architecture is described in Figure 1. Attackers may want to break into Trust Domains and then also gain access to confidential data or make unauthorized modifications to data or software running in Trust Domains and run arbitrary code in these Trust Domains [4]. Attackers may also want to break the whole security model and provide techniques to be able to run arbitrary code in Intel TDX most privileged mode called SEcure Arbitration Mode (SEAM). Potential attackers may control the virtual machine monitor (VMM) component or one of the guest Trust Domains. Attackers may also utilize vulnerabilities to gain access to the system even from legacy virtual machines.

Cheng et al. [3] describe the Intel TDX threat model based on Intel documentation. Attackers can interact with the Intel TDX module, and they can

build, initialize, measure, and tear down Trust Domains. Attackers may provide invalid input to these calls trying to find vulnerabilities. Additionally, attackers may have access to physical memory and various devices in the system. Attackers may be able to read and write physical memory locations and reconfigure memory management units.

According to [3] attackers can have physical access and freely manipulate Trust Domain input data by utilizing memory access mechanisms like Direct Memory Access (DMA) or Memory-Mapped Input/Output (MMIO). Attackers can also manipulate Peripheral Component Interconnect (PCI) bus or Advanced Configuration and Power Interface (ACPI) tables. Manipulation of time and randomness functions is also protected.

Basically, attackers can control almost everything except the Intel TDX Module and the resources protected by it. Confidentiality and integrity of Trust Domains are protected, but attackers may still be able to break availability. Low-level hardware attacks, e.g., fault injections, HW-based memory rollback attacks, and various side-channel attacks, may still be possible.

3.1.3 SUMMARY

Table 1 is summarizing Intel TDX features.

Table 1. Intel TDX summary

Feature	Description
Virtualization used	TDX is using Intel VT, which provides basic virtualization support and isolation of VMs using a trusted hypervisor.
Processor modes	SEcure Arbitration Mode (SEAM) is used.
How is confidential VM started	Untrusted hypervisor (TDX-Aware Host VMM) must call Intel TDX Module using SEAMCALL instruction. TDX Module can then launch an enclave using VMLAUNCH instruction that is also normally used by hypervisors.
Components inside confidential VM	Trust Domain can run unmodified applications and paravirtualized operating systems or runtimes that are called as TDX-Enlighted operating systems.
Secure channel	Does not specify own mechanism. Refers to attested TLS.
Attestation support	TPM-like set of registers to store measurements Measurement of Trust Domain (MRTD) and four Runtime

	Measurement Registers (RTMRs). Using also SGX and SGX DCAP mechanisms for remote attestation.
Attestation evidence creation	Trust Domain (TD) is creating a TD report with caller specified nonce REPORTDATA calling TDCALL[TDG.MR.REPORT]. This report is then signed as QUOTE operation utilizing SGX Quoting Enclave (QE).
Attestation data format	Custom format. See figure 8 in [3].
Attestation verification	The verifier can use Intel Provisioning Certification Service (PCS) to retrieve TDX specific Provisioning Certification Key (PCK) certificates, revocation lists, and TCB information.
Migration support	TDX includes live migration support as a draft specification but the feature is listed as upcoming features. There will be TDX Export API and TDX Import API that can be used to migrate Trust Domain to another platform node.
VM encryption	TDX is using Intel TME and MKTME. TME can be used to encrypt the whole main memory and MKTME allows the use of multiple keys and supports page-level granularity for encryption.
Trusted I/O	Trusted I/O virtualization with TDISP capable devices [10].
TCB components	According to [11] TCB components are Intel CPU hardware, Trust Domain attestation software, Intel Authenticated Code Modules (ACM), and Intel TDX Module.
Restrictions	TDX can provide confidentiality and integrity guarantees but no availability guarantees.

3.2 AMD SEV-SNP

AMD has a long development history of secure virtual machines. Their approach is called Secure Encrypted Virtualization (SEV). AMD developed SEV as a response to Intel SGX enclaves but using a very different approach that also has many benefits as it does not have similar memory restrictions as SGX and unmodified software can be run in SEV.

3.2.1 DESCRIPTION

AMD SEV was originally announced in 2016 and there are two major upgrade versions that provided additional protection. The initial version provides confidential encrypted virtual machines. Each virtual machine has a unique encryption key and the hypervisor has no access to decrypted data. The second version is called SEV-ES (Encrypted State) and it added protection for processor registers. The hypervisor can only see encrypted registers. The third version is called SEV-SNP (Secure Nested Paging), and it added integrity protection for confidential virtual machines preventing various data replay and memory re-mapping attacks by malicious hypervisor. Different features must be configured in SEV-capable AMD processors and system software as well [12].

AMD memory encryption technology is called AMD Secure Memory Encryption (SME). There is also another option called Transparent SME (TSME) that is turning on memory encryption in an OS/Hypervisor independent way.

Figure 3. AMD SEV encrypted memory access.

AMD provides an API for hypervisors called Secure Encrypted Virtualization API [13] that can be used to launch and manage confidential virtual machines. Hosts that have AMD SEV-SNP also have another set of functions that can be used to manage confidential virtual machines [14]. AMD SEV-SNP VMs can be launched using open-source software QEMU and KVM. AMD has maintained its own patches for the Linux kernel and QEMU that support launching confidential VMs. However, since Linux kernel version 6.11 and QEMU 9.1, the feature has been merged to upstream kernels [15].

According to the AMD documentation AMD Secure Processor (ASP), also known as Platform Security Processor (PSP), is internally responsible for creating, monitoring, and maintaining the security environment. PSP is a closed-source component, but it is known to be ARM TrustZone-based co-processor for AMD systems that has a role similar to Intel Management Engine (ME). AMD SEV security platform can be extended to using TDISP capable devices using functionality that is specified in SEV-TIO specification [16], [17]. AMD SEV-SNP has added support for live migration. A new component called Migration Agent (MA) is used to assist live migrations [18].

Figure 4. AMD SEV-SNP architecture

AMD SEV-SNP remote attestation examples can be found in [19] and [20]. There are various alternatives to how attestation can be implemented. Remote attestation can either implement a DICE-based attestation scenario [21] or utilize virtual TPMs (vTPM) [22]. Virtual TPM support is typically supported by a hypervisor. However, in this case the hypervisor is untrusted and virtual TPM must be implemented at the SVSM level. Existing TPM drivers need to be modified (enlightened) to use the SVSM vTPM. However, existing user space tools for TPM handling and kernel components like IMA can be used without modifications.

Figure 5. Virtual TPMs and Confidential VMs

3.2.2 THREAT MODEL

AMD Secure Encrypted Virtualization – Secure Nested Paging (SEV-SNP) technology can be used to run confidential virtual machines and implement protection for confidentiality and integrity. A summary of mechanisms to protect against various threats can be found in Table 2 which is adapted from the AMD white paper [23] that is describing these protection mechanisms and also describes various threats.

AMD SEV-SNP is using hardware-based memory encryption to protect against various confidentiality threats like using DMA access to read memory areas or accessing virtual machine memory areas from a hypervisor. AMD SEV-SNP is also targeted to protect against various integrity threats like data replay, corruption, re-mapping, and aliasing-based attacks. Availability threats are still possible if a malicious hypervisor decides not to run VMs.

Table 2. CIA threat mitigation in different AMD SEV platforms.

Threat	Example	SEV	SEV-ES	SEV-SNP
Confidentiality				
VM Memory	Hypervisor reads private memory	Y	Y	Y
VM Register State	Read VM register state after VMEXIT	N	Y	Y
DMA Protection	Device attempts to read VM memory	Y	Y	Y

Integrity				
Replay Protection	Replace VM memory with an old copy	N	N	Y
Data Corruption	Replace VM memory with junk data	N	N	Y
Memory Aliasing	Map two guest pages to same DRAM page	N	N	Y
Memory Remapping	Switch DRAM page mapped to a guest page	N	N	Y
Availability				
DoS on Hypervisor	Malicious guest refuses to yield/exit	Y	Y	Y
DoS on Guest	Malicious hypervisor refuses to run guest	N	N	N

The white paper [23] also mentions various physical access attacks. DRAM cold boot attacks where DRAM content is analysed offline are part of the threat model and are also mitigated by all AMD SEV versions. However, hardware attacks against the memory bus when running VMs are said to be out of scope and are not mitigated in any AMD SEV versions. Other threats that are mentioned are rollback attacks against trusted computing base components. AMD SEV-SNP provides protection for those rollback attacks, but other AMD SEV versions are still vulnerable.

Optionally, AMD SEV-SNP is also able to provide some protection against attacks that try to inject interrupts and exceptions to confidential virtual machines. For example, malicious interrupt injection where researchers managed to break the execution integrity of VMs. Another attack that used malicious interrupts is WeeSee [24], where researchers used malicious #VC exceptions to leak sensitive information and inject arbitrary code into the VM. There are also mitigation mechanisms against various debugging-related attacks and falsified CPUID information. There are still threats like side-channel attacks that are not covered, see [23]. For example, fingerprinting attacks based on access patterns and performance counter information are still possible, but some protection may be available in future SEV technologies. Google Project Zero has audited the AMD SEV-based platform. Their report is publicly available [25].

3.2.3 SUMMARY

Table 3 is summarizing AMD SEV-SNP features.

Table 3. AMD SEV-SNP summary

Feature	Description
Virtualization used	Yes
Processor modes	VM Privilege Levels (VMPLs)
How is confidential VM started	Qemu/KVM is used to launch confidential VM.
Components inside confidential VM	AMD SEV-SNP can run unmodified applications, OS userspace and kernel.
Secure channel	Not specified, TLS and attested TLS sometimes mentioned.
Attestation support	AMD-SP controls attestation process.
Attestation evidence creation	AMD-SP collects platform and guest measurements and signs the attestation report
Attestation data format	Custom format including platform and guest measurements signed by Versioned Chip-Endorsement Key (VCEK).
Attestation verification	Guest owner is expected to verify the attestation report using attestation policy.
Migration support	SEV-SNP supports live migration.
VM encryption	AMD SME, TSME
Trusted I/O	SEV-TIO [16], [17] can connect TDISP capable devices.
TCB components	AMD CPUs , ASP, memory chips
Restrictions	Provides confidentiality and integrity but no availability guarantees.

3.3 RISC-V COVE

3.3.1 DESCRIPTION

RISC-V architecture includes a low-level isolation specification for memory access called Physical Memory Protection (PMP). There is also a similar specification for I/O access called IOPMP [26]. RISC-V processor architecture is also using privilege levels for executable code. In addition to typical User (U) and Supervisor (S) levels, there is the most privileged Machine (M) mode. Utilizing these low-level primitives and a couple of extensions there is a specification called Confidential VM Extension (CoVE) for Confidential Computing [27] specified by RISC-V AP-TEE WG. CoVE provides trusted, confidential virtual machines that are isolated from the rest of the system, requiring minimal TCB. Additionally, CoVE is using RISC-V hypervisor extension that adds an additional stage to address mapping and also provides new privilege levels. HS-mode is similar to the S-mode with few additional instructions. There are also the VU and VS modes replacing the U and S modes respectively.

The architecture includes the following components:

- **TEE Virtual Machine (TEE VM)** – Isolated confidential virtual machine.
- **TEE Security Manager (TSM)** – Manage TEE VMs.
- **TSM-driver** – Provide isolation to TSM.

Figure 6. RISC-V CoVE reference architecture

CoVE also includes few APIs that can be used to control CoVE. The following API functions and interrupt extensions (as SBI components) are listed in chapter 13 in [27].

- **CoVE Host Extension (COVH-ABI)** – Handles TVM lifecycle management functions, e.g., memory management, thread allocation, and scheduling.
- **CoVE Guest Extension (COVG-ABI)** – Handle attestation requests from TVM workloads and memory-sharing functions.
- **CoVE Interrupt Extension (COVI-SBI)** – Manage secure interrupt facilities.

CoVE isolation is based on memory tagging and memory controller that is able to isolate access based on a confidential qualifier and special Memory Tracking Table (MTT) as described in Figure 7. Access to confidential memory regions is enforced in hardware via a confidential qualifier maintained per a hardware thread (hart).

Figure 7. CoVE memory isolation with memory tracking table and confidential qualifier

RISC-V AP-TEE-IO WG is specifying an extension that allows secure direct access to devices assigned to confidential VMs [28]. The specification allows connecting TDISP-capable devices.

3.3.2 THREAT MODEL

RISC-V platform has a confidential virtual machine architecture specification called CoVE [27]. The RISC-V Security Model specification [29] defines an adversarial model by grouping attacks into the following categories:

- **Logical** – both the attacker and the victim are processes on the same system.
- **Physical** – the attacker has physical access to the system
- **Remote** – the attacker has neither logical nor physical access to the system but is able to attack using either networking protocols or by utilizing side channels.

Furthermore, the specification classifies the attacks as direct, indirect, and chained attacks. The indirect attacks refer to the use of side-channels and the chained attacks refer to the use of a combination of multiple attacks.

Chapter 4 of the CoVE specification [27] defines a threat model for the CoVE architecture. The specification defines an adversary model that lists attack capabilities that the adversary is able to do. The categories are:

- **Unprivileged Software Adversary** – Attacker is able to run user mode (U-mode) software.
- **System Software Adversary** – Attacker is able to manipulate kernel-level functionality running in RISC-V S-mode.
- **Startup Software Adversary** – Attacker is able to manipulate boot phase software running in M-mode.
- **Non-invasive Hardware Adversary** – Attacker is able to do passive monitoring with physical access.
- **Invasive Hardware Adversary** – Attacker is able to do hardware attacks.
- **Side/Covert Channel Adversary** – Attacker is able to do side-channel attacks and analysis.

The Cove specification [27] is then specifying a list of threats by listing multiple attacks and ways how confidential information can be exposed from the system referring to the components of the architecture with a sidenote that the list is not exhaustive. TVM security requirements are then classified with categories, security criteria, and implementation requirements (required, optional, implementation specific).

3.3.3 SUMMARY

Table 4 is summarizing CoVE features.

Table 4. RISC-V CoVE summary

Feature	Description
Virtualization used	CoVE is utilizing RISC-V Hypervisor Extension.
Processor modes	M-mode with RISC-V Physical Memory Protection (PMP) and proposed Memory Tracking Table (MTT).
How is confidential VM started	Untrusted VMM can use COVH-API call <i>sbi_covh_create_tvm()</i> to create an enclave (TVM).
Components inside confidential VM	TVM does not require application refactoring as it can support unmodified workloads. TVM workload can run in virtual user and supervisor modes, so operating systems can also be run in TVM. TVM can also include non-

	confidential memory pages that can be used as shared memory with a non-confidential system.
Secure channel	Not specified but TVM may have non-confidential (shared) memory regions that are used as buffers to implement communication channels to a non-confidential host.
Attestation support	The CoVE attestation model follows the IETF RATS Remote Attestation architecture.
Attestation evidence creation	A collection of claims and the <i>sbi_covg_get_evidence()</i> function. DICE model is also in use.
Attestation data format	CoVE is referring to IETF RATS Entity Attestation Token (EAT) specification
Attestation verification	Following conventions of IETF RATS relying party with appraisal policy.
Migration support	Not specified
VM encryption	CoVE is using memory isolation with a confidential-mode qualifier and a Memory Tracking Table (MTT). TEE memory can be encrypted.
Trusted I/O	TDISP capable devices can be connected utilizing CoVE-IO specification [CoVE-IO].
TCB components	TEE Security Manager (TSM), RISC-V CPU hardware, TSM-driver, and memory and IO controllers.
Restrictions	Development board hardware support for CoVE features, e.g., MTT and a confidential-mode qualifier does not exist. Testing with the Salus project and qemu only. Depends on many not yet ratified standard features.

3.4 ARM CCA

3.4.1 DESCRIPTION

ARM has a new security architecture concept called ARM Confidential Compute Architecture (CCA) [30], [31] that is extending their existing old TrustZone model. ARM TrustZone is splitting resources into NormalWorld and SecureWorld domains, isolating trusted SecureWorld from untrusted NormalWorld. One problem has been that this static partitioning leads to a large monolithic SecureWorld. Because implementation errors in one of the SecureWorld components could ruin the security of all SecureWorld components, system providers have been reluctant to allow third parties to add their own components to ARM TrustZone SecureWorld. This has seriously limited the potential of the platform and left SecureWorld only to system providers and their few close cooperating partner organizations.

ARM CCA, supported in ARMv9 architecture, provides a new abstraction called Realm, which is a hardware-backed isolated execution environment for confidential computing tasks that co-exists with existing NormalWorld and SecureWorld concepts. ARM Realm Management Extensions (RME) provides isolation, resource management, and attestation for realms. There can also be multiple Realms so that third parties do not need mutual trust and are also separated from traditional SecureWorld. Realms are managed by a new architecture component called Realm Management Monitor (RMM). Sample RMM implementation is available in [32]. SecureWorld is also managed by a hypervisor-level component called Secure Partition Manager (SPM). RootWorld monitor component is binding different worlds together (see Figure 8).

Because the Realm concept is only available in ARMv9-based devices, there is not yet affordable hardware to test the feature. However, ARM has provided a platform simulator and guidelines to test the feature [33].

CCA is a proprietary ARM-specific concept. However, it is a good example of the challenges of building such systems. It could also be used as a building block for new cross-platform confidential computing systems that could utilize ARM CCA Realms and cooperate with non-ARM components. ARM is also adopting PCI-SIG TDISP [34] and IDE [35] to allow realms to connect trusted devices. Veraison [36] can be used as an attestation verification service.

Figure 8. ARM Confidential Compute Architecture

3.4.2 THREAT MODEL

ARM CCA is meant to protect the confidentiality and integrity of data that is processed in the enclave. The model does not provide availability guarantees. Li et al. [31] describe ARM CCA protection mechanisms in attack cases where there is no physical access. However, the attacker is assumed to be able to compromise the hypervisor and other system software components be able to manipulate memory and registers. The attack model also includes DMA-based attacks.

ARM CCA specification is flexible in protection mechanisms requiring baseline protection but allowing different implementations to provide more features. For example, memory encryption can be implemented in a world-unique manner (e.g., different encryption for SecureWorld, NormalWorld, and Realm) or each Realm could have own unique encryption key [30].

3.4.3 SUMMARY

Table 5 summarizes ARM CCA features.

Table 5. ARM CCA summary

Feature	Description
Virtualization used	ARM CCA RMM is running in EL2 level that is reserved for hypervisors.
Processor modes	The monitor component also known as Root World is running in EL3 level. RMM is running in EL2 privilege level. Realm software is running in EL1 (supervisor) and EL0 (user) privilege levels respectively.
How is confidential VM started	Realm enclave is started by the RMM component. There is Realm Management Interface (RMI) that allows NormalWorld (normally hypervisor) to interact with RMM and Realm Service Interface (RSI) that RMM is using to interact with Realm software.
Components inside confidential VM	Realm Service Interface (RSI) components. Optionally also intra-realm separation (planes, paravisor) that allows system services to be isolated from the guest OS. This is a new feature.
Secure channel	Attested TLS is proposed.
Attestation support	ARM CCA is following IETF RATS attestation architecture with platform specific adaptations.
Attestation evidence creation	RMM collects the information and build attestation evidence.
Attestation data format	Draft specification is in https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ffm-rats-cca-token/
Attestation verification	Project Veraison can be used to build attestation verification service.
Migration support	No
VM encryption	Realm-world-wide encryption called Memory Encryption Contexts (MEC). This is a new feature.

Trusted I/O	PCI-SIG TDISP [34] and IDE [35] specifications allow realms to connect trusted devices.
TCB components	Monitor, RMM, SPM (and other SecureWorld components)
Restrictions	Provides confidentiality and integrity to realms but no availability guarantees.

3.5 SUMMARY

All platforms share similar features and have a goal to provide confidentiality to unmodified computing workloads when those tasks are run in a confidential VM. AMD SEV-SNP has been an example for Intel TDX and RISC-V CoVE security architectures. ARM CCA is an extension to older TrustZone-based security architectures providing support for third-party confidential computing tasks.

AMD SEV-SNP and Intel TDX are specifications from processor manufacturers and matching implementations can be found from their newest processor versions. ARM licensees are supposed to implement at least the baseline CCA functionality but can also include additional optional features of the specification. RISC-V CoVE is a newcomer, and the specification is still not ratified. It is also in the same position as ARM as manufacturers may support different feature sets.

Table 6. TEEs comparisons

Feature	Intel TDX	AMD SEV-SNP	RISC-V CoVE	ARM CCA
Attestation measurement	Hash of the initial state and four Runtime Measurement Registers	Hash of the initial state	Hash of the initial state	Hash of the initial state
Attestation format	Custom format	Custom format	IETF RATS EAT specification format	IETF RATS EAT (draft CCA profile)
Secure channel	Does not specify own mechanism	Does not specify own mechanism	Memory regions that are used as	Attested TLS is proposed

			buffers can be implemented as communication channels to a non-confidential host.	
Components inside confidential VM	Unmodified applications and paravirtualized operating systems	Unmodified applications and OS userspace and kernel	Unmodified workloads can be run, for example an unmodified OS	Realm Service Interface (RSI) components
Migration support	None, but upcoming	Supported	Not specified	None

Confidential VMs are able to provide confidentiality for workloads that are processed isolating computation from the host system and also from other confidential VMs. This is achieved either by strong hardware-based isolation (e.g., ARM TrustZone) or by using encryption for VMs. Integrity verification can be done also externally by using remote attestation for confidential VMs. However, availability is not guaranteed as malicious hypervisor may decide not to allow execution for confidential VMs.

4 TOOLS

There are frameworks that allow software development to multiple hardware platforms hiding implementation details from the developer and expanding deployment alternatives to multiple platforms. However, typically these frameworks support only two hardware platforms. According to a survey article by Paju et al. [37] Intel SGX and AMD SEV are the most supported platforms. There are also lots of ARM TrustZone-related projects.

In this section we are presenting examples of these frameworks. The section also includes examples of ARM and RISC-V platforms.

4.1 ENARX

Enarx [38] [Enarx] is an open-source solution for running applications in TEEs. Enarx's name for a hardware TEE is Keep. The Keep architecture can be seen in Figure 9. It supports multiple hardware solutions for TEEs, such as AMD SEV and Intel SGX, and provides WebAssembly runtime (WASM) [39]. Enarx also implements its attestation service called Steward, which verifies the attestation report. The attestation report can be either Intel SGX or AMD SEV attestation report. Another component of Enarx is a workload repository called Drawbridge. This component lets Enarx Keeps download workloads directly from Drawbridge after Steward verifies the attestation report.

Enarx provides multiple platform support hiding platform-specific details to the hardware abstraction layer both for process-based SGX enclaves and virtual machine-based AMD SEV TEEs by introducing a platform-specific shim layer. Enarx also includes WebAssembly runtime with WebAssembly System Interface (WASI) [40]. Enarx API is based on the WASI API that is still in development. Because there are many languages that can be targeted to WebAssembly, Enarx applications can be built using multiple languages (e.g., C/C++, Go, Python, Java, Rust).

Figure 9. Enarx Keep Architecture.

The flow of the execution is the following:

1. The Attestation phase in which Enarx checks that the host to which you are planning to deploy is a genuine TEE instance. The Steward does the verification and validation steps. It is recommended that the user also verifies the Enarx TEE.
2. The Packaging phase is where the Enarx management component encrypts the application and any required data.
3. The Provisioning phase is when Enarx sends the application and data to the Enarx TEE for execution.

Enarx is a fully open-source project (available on GitHub) with an Apache-2.0 license and most of the code is in Rust programming language.

4.2 VERACRUZ

Veracruz [41] is a framework for defining and deploying collaborative, privacy-preserving computations among a group of mutually mistrusting individuals. Veracruz uses robust isolation technology (a mixture of trusted hardware or high-assurance hypervisor-based isolation) and remote attestation protocols to establish a safe, "neutral ground" within which a collaborative computation occurs on an untrusted device. Veracruz uses, just as Enarx, WebAssembly to run computations utilizing WASM and WASI.

Veracruz has been evaluated in a research paper by Brossard et al. [42] where Veracruz has been tested with AWS Nitro Enclaves, a dedicated isolated hardware provided by Amazon to AWS web services. Another tested platform is Raspberry Pi4 configuration using software-based isolation with IceCap hypervisor that is utilizing seL4 microkernel. The paper also mentions that there is support for ARM CCA Realms.

Veracruz can delegate attestation verification to platform-specific attestation services. Proxy attestation service communicates with the device sending an attestation request and receiving the report. The proxy is then sending the report to platform-specific attestation service.

Veracruz principals are assumed to have certain roles that are specified in the global policy configuration together with the identity information of the principals. Brossard et al. [42] present a use case where mutually distrusting principals are expected to perform secure computation for sensitive data. The result can be returned to a principal that has access neither to software nor data. The program owner can upload software and data owner data to Veracruz Trusted Virtual Machine using a TLS connection. After processing data the result can be returned to another principal.

Figure 10. Veracruz computation with mutually distrusting principals.

There has not been much activity anymore in the Veracruz project this year and the last official release is from year 2022. Also, this project is using mostly Rust programming language and is licensed under the MIT license.

4.3 OAK

Oak [43] is an open-source software platform from Google that can be used to build externally verifiable distributed systems utilizing a TEE-based root of trust. Oak supports AMD SEV-SNP and Intel TDX hardware, and major parts of the system are written using Rust programming language and licensed using Apache 2.0 license.

In order to minimize a trusted computing base, Oak recommends the use of split architecture where an application is split into enclave and host parts. Enclave

applications run inside TEE and host applications can be run in an untrusted host. The role of the host application is to act as a front-end or proxy to the enclave application. External client applications are able to set up an encrypted channel to the enclave application via an untrusted host application.

Oak provides two runtime alternatives for the enclave applications. Oak Restricted Kernel alternative is a minimal microkernel that is meant to run a single application on one CPU only. Another alternative is Oak Container which can include full Linux kernel and related userspace components from Linux distributions. Oak Restricted Kernel with Oak Enclave application has a small, trusted computing base but requires more effort to partition the application in such a way that critical parts can be included in the enclave application. The Oak Container approach does not require such partitioning work, but it adds many components to the trusted computing base.

Figure 11. Oak split architecture with secure channel

Oak is meant to be externally verifiable by a remote attestation mechanism. Oak has adopted a staged approach to integrity measurements by utilizing the Device Identifier Composition Engine (DICE) approach [44] by Trusted Computing Group (TCG).

Health data related use cases for Project Oak are presented in [45]. The added value is envisioned to be enhanced privacy for data access and new privacy-aware health applications.

4.4 OPEN ENCLAVE

Open Enclave SDK [46] is an open-source cross-platform tool to develop TEE-based applications utilizing unified enclave abstraction. Intel SGX and ARM

TrustZone with OP-TEE are supported. Open Enclave is based on C/C++ code with an MIT license. Open Enclave is based on a model that splits applications into trusted and untrusted components called host and enclave respectively. Figure 12 describes the model:

Figure 12. Open Enclave split model architecture.

OpenEnclave provides a generalized enclave application model as it supports two very different platforms, Intel SGX and ARM TrustZone, removing vendor-specific signing and verification requirements. Pluggable architecture also allows the selection of different runtimes and cryptographic libraries. The SDK is available for Windows and Linux and it is also available¹ as open-source on GitHub.

4.5 APACHE TEACLAVE

Teaclave [47] provides tools to build applications utilizing TEEs for Intel SGX and ARM TrustZone platforms. Teaclave is an incubator project of the Apache Software Foundation (ASF), naturally with Apache 2.0 license. The incubator projects want to adopt the Apache style of governance and operation and to become a top-level Apache project. The project provides several APIs to develop

¹ OpenEnclave source code - <https://github.com/openenclave/openenclave>

TEE-based applications. The project implements split application pattern where the host-side application is accessing enclave code.

Teaclave SGX SDK can be used to write Intel SGX applications using the Rust programming language. The SDK is also known as RustSGX SDK. The project also includes C and Rust-based sample code, starting from a hello world application to more complex like remote attestation and secret sharing examples. The project has also implemented attested TLS based on [48]. The SDK is available as a docker image and can also work without SGX support for development purposes.

Teaclave TrustZone SDK provides examples and tools to build Rust-based host and enclave applications (Trusted Applications) to OP-TEE. The SDK provides Rust API both for host-side Rich OS Execution Environment (REE), e.g., Linux and trusted application operations. These are basically equivalent to Global Platform TEE Client API and TEE Internal API (see section 4.8) as described in Figure 13.

Figure 13. The architecture of Teaclave for TrustZone

Teaclave also includes Client SDK. There are actually two versions. One for Rust and another for Python. The project has also a Rust-based client application skeleton for the Android platform.

4.6 ISLET

Islet [49] is built on top of ARM CCA but it is also implementing its own CCA RMM component using Rust programming language. Islet is an example of how ARM CCA could be utilized to build new hardware-backed security frameworks. In addition to server-side protection, the Islet website also promotes the use of confidential computing to protect sensitive information in user devices.

Islet also includes implementation of CCA Hardware Enforced Security (HES) component that could be separate SoC and implement boot measurements.

Figure 14. Islet architecture

Islet SDK is a Rust-based open-source SDK that can be used to build applications for ARM CCA enclaves supporting sealing, attestation, and secure channel establishment. Islet SDK is also available for C/C++ applications using headers generated with the `cbindgen`² tool.

² <https://github.com/mozilla/cbindgen>

4.7 KEYSTONE

RISC-V architecture does not yet have a widely used high-level hardware-backed protection framework, but there are specifications for low-level protection that can be used as building blocks to construct higher-level abstractions. RISC-V architecture provides privilege levels for code execution. In addition to typical user-mode (U) for user space and supervisor-mode (S) for kernel space, there is also the most privileged level called machine-mode (M). There is also a low-level memory isolation protection mechanism called Physical Memory Protection (PMP) (section 3.6 in [50]). PMP can be used to configure memory regions to have different access attributes (read/write/execute). PMP configuration can be done in M-mode only. There is also work going on to extend the PMP mechanism to peripheral devices [51].

Keystone framework [52] is an open-source project that can be used to build isolated and trusted execution environments (so-called enclaves) for RISC-V devices that can utilize PMP configurations. The basic components of Keystone are described in Figure 15.

Figure 15. The components of the Keystone framework.

Keystone includes a trusted component called Security Monitor that runs in M-mode and is capable of setting up an environment for isolated enclaves and also mediates communications between untrusted components and the enclaves. Keystone enclave software is split into runtime and application components. The framework can have different runtime components. Keystone project has developed Eyrie and seL4 runtimes. Keystone Security Monitor has been implemented as a plugin of OpenSBI [53] which is an open-source implementation of RISC-V Supervisor Binary Interface (SBI) [54]. SBI provides a

communication mechanism between S- and M-modes. Untrusted applications can communicate with enclaves by using registered messages called ecalls and enclave applications may use services from untrusted side using messages called ocalls. Although Keystone is tied to RISC-V and there have not been attempts to port it to any other architecture, it serves as an example of how similar frameworks could be implemented on the RISC-V platform.

4.8 GLOBAL PLATFORM APIS

Global Platform [55] is an industry consortium that has standardized APIs for Trusted Execution Environments. These APIs are typically used in ARM TrustZone-based systems and there is also an open-source implementation called OP-TEE [56]. There are two main specifications:

- **TEE Internal API** – Specifies functions that are used in an application running in ARM SecureWorld [57]. These applications are called Trusted Applications (TAs).
- **TEE Client API** – Specifies how NormalWorld applications can interact with SecureWorld TAs [58].

Although these specifications are mainly targeted for ARM TrustZone, there are attempts to use especially TEE Internal API also in other platforms. Suzuki et al. [59] have implemented GlobalPlatform TEE Internal API in Keystone (RISC-V) and Intel SGX. OP-TEE has also been ported to RISC-V architecture by Nuclei Software [60], [61].

Figure 16. Global Platform TEE architecture.

4.9 SUMMARY

There are many tools that provide tools to build confidential computing applications with different sets of platform support. Many projects have selected Rust programming language to implement their projects. There are also different programming models. One approach is to use the bytecode interpreter approach based on the WebAssembly format. Most tools implement a split application pattern where an application is split into an insecure host part and a secure enclave part. This adds a burden for programmers as they need to partition software to use this abstraction. The confidential virtual machine approach is packing the whole application to TEE requiring quite a large TEE free from restrictions. The examples typically do not yet include support for newer platforms like AMD SEV-SNP, Intel TDX, ARM CCA support is limited to only a few platforms (typically just two platforms are supported) and RISC-V is typically not yet supported. A summary of analysed platforms is in Table 7.

Table 7. Summary of tools

Project	Platforms	Language	License	Category
Enarx	AMD SEV, Intel SGX	Rust	Apache 2.0	WebAssembly
Veracruz	AWS Nitro, SW hypervisor	Rust	MIT	WebAssembly
Oak	AMD SEV- SNP, Intel TDX	Rust	Apache 2.0	VM/container or split app
Open Enclave	Intel SGX, ARM TrustZone	C/C++	MIT	Split app
Apache Teachan	Intel SGX, ARM TrustZone	Rust	Apache 2.0	Split app
Islet	ARM CCA	Rust	Apache 2.0	VM
Keystone	RISC-V	C	BSD	Split app

Global Platform APIs	ARM TrustZone	C	BSD ³	Split app
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DRAFT

³ OP-TEE open source implementation

5 ATTESTATION

Attestation is a process in which one side (the attester) collects information about itself and sends that information to the relying party (the client) so that the relying party can verify the attester. The successful verification proves to the relying party that the SVM runs the expected code on the expected hardware and is configured correctly. If the attester is deemed trustworthy, the relying party will send confidential code/data to the attester. The process of attestation is important because it provides information about the hardware platform that is being used for confidential computing.

There are three types of attestation based on where the attester and the relying party are.

- **Local attestation** - The relying party and the attester are on the same machine.
- **Remote attestation** - The relying party and the attester are on different machines.
- **Mutual attestation** - The relying party and the attester are both running inside a TEE and want to attest each other.

In the context of hardware support for confidential computing, remote attestation is of the utmost interest to us.

5.1 REMOTE ATTESTATION PROCEDURES ARCHITECTURE (RATS)

IETF RATS working group has proposed an architecture for the process of attestation [62]. The roles defined in the architecture are:

- **Attester** - an entity that wants to prove its authenticity and integrity. This entity generates evidence. The evidence is often called the attestation report.
- **Verifier** - an entity that uses evidence and additional information to verify the attestation report (evidence) it got from the attester. It then sends the attestation results to the relying party.
- **Relying party** - the entity/client that wants to send sensitive data or code to the attester but needs assurance that the attester is secure.
- **Endorser** - an entity, typically the manufacturer, whose information (endorsements) can help verify the evidence. The endorsements are usually the information about the integrity of the evidence. For example,

the endorser for AMD SEV-SNP is the AMD Key Distribution System (KDS), from which the user can download the certificates that are used to verify the signature of the attestation report of AMD SEV-SNP confidential VMs (CVM). The signature is the proof that the CVM is booted on SEV-SNP-enabled CPU.

- **Reference value provider** - an entity, typically the manufacturer, that provides reference values to the verifier.
- **Verifier Owner** - an entity that produces appraisal policies for evidence that the verifier uses.
- **Relying Party Owner** - an entity that produces appraisal policy for attestation results that the relying party uses.

Figure 17. IETF RATS actors and information flow

The information that is being passed from one entity to another in is:

- **Evidence** - set of claims about the attesting environment. It contains information about the software and hardware used by the TEE. In the case of Intel and AMD, the evidence is a hardware-signed report with the mentioned information.
- **Endorsements** - represent a secure statement or a set of claims, in an open format, that some entity (e.g., a manufacturer) vouches for the integrity of the device's various capabilities.
- **Reference values** - are a set of values that represent the current "nominal values" of claims inside the evidence.
- **Attestation results** - carry information about the result of verifying the evidence. The attestation result can be a set of boolean values about the

set of claims of the evidence. The Verifier signs the attestation result for the Relying party to trust the attestation result.

- **Appraisal policies** - specify what claims in evidence or the attestation results are valid based on reference values and endorsements.

In the case of TEEs, the attester would be the secure enclave. The endorser and reference value provider would be the hardware TEE manufacturers, for example, AMD or Intel.

The proposed attestation architecture has two models for attestation flow: the passport model and the background-check model. In the passport model, the attester sends the evidence to the verifier, and the verifier verifies the report and sends the attestation results back to the attester. The attester can then use the obtained evidence to provide the relying parties with proof of integrity and authenticity. Upon receiving the attestation results, the relying party should also check the attestation appraisal policy. This verification model may fail in one of the following situations:

- The verifier may not give a positive attestation result.
- The verifier may not be accessible.
- The relying party may reject the attestation results based on the attestation result appraisal policy.

In the background-check model the attester send an evidence to a relying party. The relying party then forwards the evidence to the verifier. These two models differ in who is sending the evidence to verification.

5.2 ENTITY ATTESTATION TOKEN

IETF RATS WG has also specified a message data format for claims about an entity. The claims are typically about the hardware and the software running on a device. These are used to create trust between a device and a remote actor that may communicate with the device. The message format is called Entity Attestation Token (EAT) [63]. This message is also known as attestation evidence or attestation report. The specification defines two encodings for the format. There is a compact binary format utilizing Concise Binary Object Representation (CBOR) [64] and a text-based format using JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) [65].

5.3 ATTESTED TLS

We have seen that attestation is used to prove the TEE's trustworthiness to the user. The client or the relying party needs to verify the attestation report and send confidential data to the TEE if the verification is successful. This process implies the creation of a secure channel between the relying party and the TEE. We are going to focus on Transport Layer Security (TLS) to create a secure channel.

The TLS (Transport Layer Security) handshake protocol enables secure communication over the internet. It establishes a secure client and server connection by negotiating cryptographic parameters, authenticating participants, and securely exchanging encryption keys.

The creation of the TLS channel needs to be bound to the attestation report so that the relying party can be sure that the TLS channel endpoints are the TEE and the relying party. For that purpose, we can define three types of combinations of attestation and TLS. They are all called by attested TLS, but the only difference is the evidence generation time.

- Pre-handshake attestation
- Post-handshake attestation
- Intra-handshake attestation

Pre-handshake implies that the attestation evidence is generated before the TLS handshake. Intel proposed a solution in its white paper [48]. The attestation report is attached to the x.509 certificate as an extension. This way, the report is bound to the certificate. The keys for the certificate must be generated inside the TEE and stored securely. The problem with this approach is that the user cannot guarantee the freshness of the evidence, which can lead to replay attacks [66].

In post-handshake attestation, the attestation report is fetched after the TLS handshake. This solution can guarantee freshness of the evidence, but establishing the connection can have high latency

Intra-handshake attestation implies that the evidence is generated each time a client (relying party) connects to the attester (TEE). In this approach, the attestation report is generated each time a TLS connection is established, and the AR is bound to the TLS connection using TLS extensions. IETF is working on standardizing the Attested TLS mechanism [67]. The attestation report or evidence is transported in the draft using the client's Certificate message and/or the server's Certificate. The draft supports the background check and the

passport model of attestation defined in RATS. Based on the used model, a couple of new TLS extensions are defined.

The client includes the `evidence_proposal` and/or `evidence_request` extensions in the ClientHello message for the background check model.

- `evidence_proposal` extension indicates the evidence types that the client can provide to the server.
- `evidence_request` extension contains a list of evidence types the client challenges the server to provide.

The appropriate extension is used based on who has the role of the attester, the client, or the server. The server replays to the received extensions with the same extensions sent in the EncryptedExtensions message.

- `evidence_proposal` is sent as a response to the client's `evidence_proposal` extension, which indicates what types of evidence the client should provide in the client's Certificate message.
- `evidence_request` is sent as a response to the client's `evidence_request` extension, and it contains the evidence type that will be sent to the server's Certificate message.

In the passport model, the results of the attestation report verification and validation are used in TLS instead of the evidence. The results are transferred as part of the Certificate message. The client includes the `result_proposal` and/or `result_request` extensions in the ClientHello message.

- `result_proposal` indicates the verifier identities from which the client can provide the attestation results.
- `results_request` indicates the verifier identities of those from whom the client expects the server to provide the attestation results.

The appropriate extension is used based on who has the role of the attester, the client, or the server. The server replays to the received extensions with the same extensions sent in the EncryptedExtensions message.

- `result_proposal` is sent as a response to the client's `result_proposal` extension, which indicates what verifier the client should use to generate results. The evidence is provided in the client's Certificate message.
- `results_request` is sent as a response to the client's `results_request` extension, and it contains the identity of the verifier that the server will use to generate attestation results. The identity of the verifier is part of the server's Certificate message.

Using extensions enables the attester to generate a fresh attestation report. To prove the freshness of the report, the client and the server that requests the attestation report need to use a random nonce in the generation mechanism of the attestation report. The random nonce needs to be provided by the verifier that will verify the attestation report. Thus preventing replay attacks.

5.4 ATTESTATION VERIFICATION SERVICE

Remote attestation requires that the verifier has access to reference values (see Figure 17). The verifier must be aware of all valid configurations and different software versions. This can already be a very complex situation, but if there is a need to do remote attestation verification to heterogeneous systems, there might be different attestation evidence and reference value formats. Project Veraison is creating software components that can be used to develop an Attestation Verification Service that supports multiple formats [36], [68], [69]. Veraison is basically the verifier component in Figure 17. Also, EnactTrust⁴ has developed an attestation-as-a-service (a3s) software solution that can be used to monitor Arm-based IoT devices.

For example, IETF RATS WG has a standardized attestation evidence format as an Entity Attestation Token (EAT), but there can still be different profiles and alternative formats. ARM Platform Security Architecture (PSA) can use the EAT PSA profile [70] but ARM Confidential Compute Architecture (CCA) has defined another profile [71]. Remote attestation for TPM-based systems is standardized in RFC9683 [72]. Also, reference integrity values can be delivered in many different formats. One alternative is the CoRIM format [73] and there is also an ISO/IEC standard for software identification [74] and its adaptation as RFC9393 [75]. The result of the attestation verification can be returned to a relying party using the EAT Attestation Result (EAR) format [76]. There is also another specification that is how to deliver specification attestation results for secure interactions [77].

The goal of the Veraison project is to support a number of different formats and also to provide extensible architecture for the attestation verification service that can include additions.

⁴ EnactTrust – <https://enacttrust.com/>

6 ACCELERATORS

General-purpose CPUs are flexible and can be programmed to execute all kinds of software. However, sometimes general purpose CPU is not optimal for certain tasks. There is a need to offload computation tasks to a co-processor or an accelerator component. For example, cryptographic operations can utilize a special-purpose cryptographic accelerator hardware that is optimized to execute cryptographic operations. This has multiple benefits. The accelerator is, by default, faster than the main CPU in these operations. Offloading is also releasing the main CPU to execute other tasks while the accelerator is calculating cryptographic operations. There can also be additional benefits, e.g., power-efficient accelerators in mobile devices. From a security architecture perspective, these accelerators can be a problem if data must be transferred outside from the protected system on a chip (SoC) to a peripheral device using some kind of bus. The bus connection can be monitored and manipulated.

6.1 GPU ACCELERATORS

Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) are perhaps the most well-known accelerators. Originally these were used to accelerate computer game graphics. However, soon it was realized that these accelerators could also be used in cryptocurrency mining and AI/ML training and inference computing tasks. Also cloud providers have added GPUs to their offerings in order to support demand, especially related to AI/ML.

Attaching accelerators to secure computing systems requires trusted I/O solutions that can be used to extend the security perimeter. TEE Device Interface Security Protocol (TDISP) specification provides a way to securely add peripheral devices to the trusted virtual machine. The specification is available only for PCI-SIG consortium members but the main functionality is shared in public. TDISP allows establishing a trust relationship between a trusted virtual machine and a trusted device, securing the interconnect between the host and device, and attaching and detaching a trusted device to a trusted virtual machine in a trusted manner [34]. Devices that follow TDISP specifications are said to be TDISP capable. Another specification that supports the secure interconnect of accelerators is the Security Protocol and Data Model (SPDM) [78] by the Distributed Management Task Force (DMTF).

Nvidia Hopper architecture has added confidential computing support for Nvidia GPUs [79], allowing confidential VMs to securely utilize GPU functionality using an SPDM channel. Nvidia GPU can be connected to AMD SEV-SNP or Intel TDX CPUs, extending TEE to include a GPU accelerator. Additionally, there can be an

encrypted Nvlink GPU-GPU connection. Application developers can use Nvidia's Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) Toolkit to utilize accelerator functionality inside the confidential VM in a similar way as CUDA is used outside of the confidential VM.

When Nvidia GPU boots in confidential computing mode (CC-On) confidential VM can also request attestation from the GPU. The attestation report can be verified by utilizing the Nvidia Remote Attestation Service (NRAS) and the GPU device certificate can be validated using the Nvidia Online Certificate Service Protocol (OCSP) service.

Figure 18. Extending TEE to Nvidia GPUs with encrypted channels (red arrows).

Intel has a built-in accelerator for AI workloads called Intel Advanced Matrix Extensions (AMX) [80]. As it is implemented inside SoC, it does not have a similar interconnect problem as external accelerators.

6.2 FPGA ACCELERATORS

Hardware manufacturers develop solutions for tasks that are most in demand. However, customers might have computing tasks that could have efficient hardware-based implementations but the market is too small for big manufacturers like Nvidia. Hardware-based implementation can also be a new innovative way to solve the problem. Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) is a programmable hardware platform that can be used to implement hardware and test it with real-world problems. FPGA can also be used to simulate computer systems. It is not the most efficient use of the platform, as the main benefit would come from the utilization of

parallelism. Because FPGA is reconfigurable, it is possible to use a dedicated accelerator that best fits a current workload.

Cloud providers have also started to offer FPGA platforms allowing customers to upload their own hardware accelerators for cloud computing. For example, Amazon has an Amazon EC2 F1 FPGA platform [81]. These platforms also require trust for the cloud platform provider and include complex trust relationships [82]. There are attempts to develop confidential computing for FPGA. ShEF provides a secure boot and remote attestation mechanism and can be used to run shielded enclaves [83] in FPGA hardware hosted by a cloud service provider. ShEF relies on the partial reconfiguration feature of high-end FPGAs and requires that the FPGA manufacturer has embedded keys security kernel that are used in secure boot. IP providers and data owners are other actors in the ShEF FPGA use case. IP providers and data owners must trust the FPGA manufacturer but not the cloud service provider and its FPGA components.

Another example that could be applied also to confidential computing cloud service use is MeetGo [84]. MeetGo assumes that the FPGA board includes a master key pair (MK) as a trust anchor and a dedicated module called the security agent (SA). MeetGo assumes that the MK_{priv} is installed into the device and MK_{pub} can be distributed to remote users. There are two alternatives to install the MK_{priv} :

- MK_{priv} can be included in the SA bitstream. This means that each FPGA instance must have its own bitstream. This approach is compatible with existing FPGA hardware, but the requirement for instance-specific bitstreams, is a bit inconvenient.
- MK_{priv} can be stored in non-volatile memory like e-fuse. This may require hardware changes and is not compatible with existing FPGA hardware. Also, the MK_{priv} should be accessible only from the SA component. MeetGo recommends encrypting the stored MK_{priv} and to store the decryption key to the SA bitstream that now can be common for all FPGA instances.

MeetGo assumes that the SA is loaded first to the FPGA board using a secure bitstream loading mechanism that prevents tampering of the stream and also provides confidentiality. MeetGo applications are loaded utilizing partial reconfiguration that allows a part of the FPGA to be modified by loading partial bitstreams when the system is running. FPGA can be partitioned at boot time to support regions with different reprogramming options. The SA is loaded into static area and FPGA

applications to the dynamic area that supports runtime modifications, but the SA is the only entity that is authorized to access the dynamic area where applications are installed. Application loading is handled by the SA and the SA takes care of the verification. MeetGo implements communications between the SA and the loaded applications. SA is also used to establish a secure communication channel between the remote user and an application running in the FPGA.

6.3 FHE ACCELERATORS

This document is mainly covering hardware alternatives to implement confidential computing by utilizing TEEs. Another approach to confidential computing is to use fully homomorphic encryption that can be used to process encrypted data. Unfortunately, fully homomorphic encryption has a very large performance penalty. However, there has been growing interest to develop accelerators to speed up also fully homomorphic encryption computations.

FHE acceleration state of the art is described in a recent survey by Zhang et al. [85] where they have compared designs of 14 different FHE accelerators and also evaluated open-source implementations. One approach is to pack many plaintext messages into one ciphertext and then utilize Single Instruction/Multiple Data (SIMD)-like operations in parallel. However, the key thing is an efficient calculation of Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) or more generic Number Theoretic Transform (NTT). Intel Homomorphic Encryption Acceleration Library (HEXL) implementation is using Intel vector instructions [86] to boost computation. There are also libraries that are using general-purpose GPU frameworks (e.g., CUDA) for implementation. However, these general-purpose accelerators do not yet give enough performance improvement to make FHE practical. FPGA or custom Application-Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) implementations have been proposed to overcome the challenge. According to Zhang et al. the growing trend is to move to custom ASICs instead of using GPUs or FPGA-based designs. They also note that new accelerators are more and more based on software/hardware co-design where hardware-friendly algorithms are selected first and then combined with adaptable software components. These accelerators can also provide enhanced programmability and support for an unlimited depth of operations.

Another set of problems that has received less attention than server-side FHE acceleration is how resource-constrained clients could interact with FHE cloud services. The client must encode and encrypt the input and then decrypt and decode the output. This requires considerable resources from resource-

constrained clients. Aloha-HE [87] is an open-source⁵ FPGA-based accelerator for the FHE client-side operations produced by the University of Technology Graz implementing the client-side operations of the Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song (CKKS) scheme [88].

Figure 19. The CKKS client-side operations.

There are multiple Aloha-HE FPGA implementations. One implementation also supports low-end Xilinx Zynq-7000 series FPGA boards that also include hardcore CPUs that can be used as a host processor for FPGA implementation. Zedboard⁶ is a typical Zynq-7000 development board. Linux kernel includes an FPGA manager component that can be used to program bitstreams to Zynq-7000 boards⁷.

Nowadays there are also low-end development boards (e.g., BeagleV Fire⁸) that include a small reprogrammable FPGA. These platforms can be used to test these FHE client-side operations. Low-end FPGA boards typically do not support partial reconfiguration.

⁵ Aloha-HE source code - <https://github.com/flokrieger/Aloha-HE>

⁶ Zedboard Zynq-7000 FPGA board - <https://digilent.com/reference/programmable-logic/zedboard/start>

⁷ Linux FPGA manager - <https://xilinx-wiki.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/A/pages/18841645/Solution+Zynq+PL+Programming+With+FPGA+Manager>

⁸ BeagleV-Fire - <https://www.beagleboard.org/boards/beaglev-fire>

7 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The architecture model that we are defining contains an isolated execution environment that is isolated from the rest of the system by hardware means. Most of the mentioned components in this section will be expanded upon in more detail in deliverable 2.3, which includes the TEE toolkit.

The main requirement of the architecture is that it must protect the confidentiality and integrity of the data that is processed. The architecture should also easily support workloads without extensive modifications. It should be possible to deploy existing computing task to confidential virtual machine. The architecture should also be platform agnostic so that it is possible to easily utilize new computing platforms when those platforms become available. The system should support multiple confidential computing hardware platforms. There should be a mechanism to verify the integrity and authenticity of the computing platform. There should be a communication mechanism between the confidential virtual machine and the external host. The number of TCB components should be minimal.

7.1 ARCHITECTURE REQUIREMENTS

CONFIDENTIAL6G technical report D3.1 [1] contains a list of confidential computing requirements. A couple of requirements are explicitly targeted for TEE implementation. In this section we will discuss on how these requirements can be fulfilled based on our prototype implementation Cocos AI [89]. Cocos AI provides a Go-based API for common TEE operations.

Table 8. TEE-related requirements and Cocos AI.

Requirement	Cocos AI implementation
#1: System SHOULD provide a consistent, vendor-agnostic API for common TEE operations.	Cocos AI provides Go-based API that can be used to hide platform specific details. The requirement explicitly requires a secure way for data storage and retrieval, key generation and management, remote attestation, communication, and execution of code.
#2: System SHOULD automatically detect and configure available TEEs.	In most cases we have static configuration and Cocos AI adapted to supported platform.

#3: System SHOULD provide users a mechanism to choose the desired TEE or let the System select the most suitable one.	This requirement may be supported later because currently most configurations are expected to have only one TEE alternative.
#4: System MUST provide mechanism to verify the authenticity and integrity of TEE environments.	This requirement is more for the underlying platform. It must support secure or trusted boot, have certified identity, and support remote attestation. Cocos AI can be used to request remote attestation.
#5: System SHOULD allow users to create and manage secure enclaves within TEEs.	This is basic functionality of Cocos AI.
#6: System MUST enable the secure destruction of enclaves when no longer needed.	This is a requirement for the underlying platform.
#7: System MUST Ensure the secure deletion of sensitive data from the TEE.	This is a requirement for the underlying platform
#8: System SHOULD provide mechanism to manage cryptographic keys within the TEE, ensuring secure storage and usage.	Cocos AI should have mechanisms for this.

7.2 HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE

7.2.1 INTRODUCTION

High-level architecture includes the following actors.

- **Manager** - Software component that is responsible for managing and starting the confidential virtual machines.
- **Agent** - Software component that runs inside the confidential virtual machine and controls the computation execution. The role of the agent is also to form a secure channel with the clients.
- **Client** - Software component that runs in non-trusted host and communicates with the agent running inside the confidential virtual machine. The command line interface application (CLI).

- **Verifier** – Software component that can be used to verify received attestation evidence against reference integrity metrics. This can be combined with the client component. The CLI also acts as a verifier.
- **Computation Management (CM)**– Cloud service to control confidential computation tasks (e.g., define computation metadata, like participants list, algorithm and data providers, result recipients).
- **Enclave OS (EOS)** – Custom lightweight Linux distribution to run workloads in a confidential virtual machine.

These actors are also shown in Figure 20 that describes the current Cocos AI implementation mainly targeted to support AMD SEV-SNP platform.

Figure 20. The Cocos AI architecture targeting AMD SEV-SNP.

Main operations for a confidential virtual machine include:

- **Create** – Create a new confidential virtual machine. Provided by the CM.
- **Start** – Start the confidential virtual machine. Provided by the CM.
- **Stop** – Stop the confidential virtual machine. Provided by the CM.
- **Delete** – Delete the confidential virtual machine. Provided by the CM.
- **Attest** – Perform remote attestation to the confidential virtual machine. Provided by the CLI.
- **Connect** – Build secure channel from untrusted host client to the confidential virtual machine. Provided by the CLI.

The following data formats are also key elements of the architecture:

- **Attestation evidence** – Data format that contains integrity proof of the platform. The attestation evidence typically contains signed measurements (cryptographic hashes) of the software components.
- **Reference integrity metrics** – Valid reference values to compare attestation evidence measurement values.

The current solution only supports AMD SEV and its newest version, AMD SEV-SNP. It is recommended that AMD SEV-SNP be used because it provides additional security features and capabilities for virtualization environments. SEV-SNP adds strong memory integrity protection to help prevent malicious hypervisor-based attacks, like data replay, memory re-mapping, and more.

The agent can fetch the attestation report from the AMD SEV-SNP secure processor. The attestation report (AR) contains, among other fields, the following:

- Measurement, a 384-bit field containing the hash of the initial guest memory.
- TCB information.
- Report data, a 512-bit field containing arbitrary data, is set using the SNP firmware ABI by the agent. The firmware does not inspect this data; it only writes it in the attestation report.
- Host data, a 256-bit field containing arbitrary data, is set using the SNP firmware ABI by the agent. The firmware does not inspect this data; it only writes it in the attestation report. The data is set in the QEMU command when the CVM is launched.
- Policy information of the CVM.
- Attestation report signature. The firmware signs the AR with a Versioned Chip Endorsement Key (VCEK) key that is derived from the chip's unique secrets and the TCB version.

The Cocos AI implementation runs in-RAM confidential VMs (CVM) so that the firmware can measure the whole CVM. The current solution relies on open-source software, more precisely, the AmdSev package of Open Virtual Machine Firmware (OVMF), QEMU, and Linux kernel to create CVMs. When the AmdSev OVMF is used, the guest memory is initialized with the OVMF, hash of the kernel, hash of the initial RAM file system (initramfs), and the kernel command line parameters, and the CVM is booted only using the OVMF, kernel, initramfs, and kernel command line parameters. This way, the measurement contains the hash of the entire CVM. Additionally, when the CVM is being booted, the OVMF gets the kernel, initramfs, and the kernel command line arguments from QEMU. OVMF then calculates the hash of the received components, and if they do not match the hashes in the initial guest memory, the CVM fails to boot. The client can

validate and verify the contents of the CVM using the attestation report and the CLI tool.

TCB contains information on the version numbers of the following components:

- Microcode version, which represents the lowest patch level of all CPU cores.
- Version of the SNP firmware.
- Version of the PSP OS version.
- Version of the PSP bootloader.

The manager uses QEMU to initialize the host data field to be the hash of the computation manifest. This data is a way to identify the booted CVM.

The policy contains information that the firmware uses to restrict the actions of the hypervisor. It includes information on whether the CVM can be activated on a single socket, the debug mode, whether simultaneous multithreading is allowed, and the minimum permitted major and minor versions of the firmware application binary interface (ABI). If the platform meets all the conditions, the hypervisor can boot the CVM.

The signature is verified using the VCEK certificate, which can be obtained from the AMD KDS. Verifying the signature gives the client the confidence that the CVM is launched on the hardware that supports SEV-SNP.

All the mentioned fields combined give the client the assurance that the CVM is running on a platform that supports AMD SEV-SNP, the verifiable contents of the CVM based on the measurement, the conditions of the booted CVM based on the policy, and the version numbers of the TCB components.

The agent and CLI use attested TLS to communicate and relay data and the algorithm from the CLI to the agent. Both software components only implement the `evidence_request` extension mentioned in section 6. The agent passes the attestation report to the CLI as an extension of the certificate message of the TLS 1.3 protocol. The agent uses the report data field of the attestation report to insert the hash of a concatenated random nonce (provided by the CLI) and the agent's TLS certificate public key. The attestation report is bound to the TLS certificate used in TLS communication using this field. The agent generates and self-signed the TLS certificate when the CVM boots. Because the whole CVM is measured and the certificate keys are generated on boot by the agent, meaning they are only known to the agent and are bound to the attestation report, the client can be sure he is connected to the agent in the CVM. The CLI generates the random nonce to guarantee the evidence's freshness. If the nonce contained in the attestation report differs from the one the CLI generated, the verification will fail, and the connection will not be established.

The client or the relying party can obtain the reference values from the computation management. The manager generates the reference values for the platform on which the manager runs. These values will become part of the attestation policy file. The client can then use the CLI to extend the attestation policy file with the expected measurement of his CVM to ensure that the correct CVM has been booted, along with the expected host data (the hash of the computation manifest). The CLI then uses this information and AMD KDS to verify and validate the attestation report. The client can also change the content of the reference information to custom values.

In the next sections more detailed view of the software architecture supporting different platforms is presented based on the 4+1 view model [90].

7.3 LOGICAL VIEW

The logical view describes the design of main classes and state machines using UML diagrams. These are based on our prototype implementation Cocos AI [89]. The pictures/figures may contain also additional methods as the pictures are based on the current implementation that has been used as a starting point. Cocos AI is implemented using Go language. Currently, the implementation supports AMD SEV-SNP but can be extended also to other platforms. Here we are presenting three main components of the system: agent, manager, and client (CLI). Support for multiple platforms is also discussed.

7.3.1 AGENT

The agent takes care of the life cycle of the computation inside the confidential virtual machine. The agent runs the computation and sends events about the status of the computation to the manager component.

The *agentService* class is implementing a *Service* interface that includes methods to receive algorithm (program) and data. There is also a method to return computation results and to handle remote attestation requests.

Figure 21. Agent service class diagram

Most of these methods are platform-agnostic Go code. However, the attestation method must call a platform-specific method to request a measurement to be used as attestation evidence. Cocos AI *quoteprovider* directory contains an implementation for AMD SEV-SNP using SEV Guest library⁹. This should be extended to support other platforms as well.

The following state machine (Figure 22) describes an agent lifecycle. The agent will receive a manifest that describes the computing task and an algorithm (program) to run computations. Cocos AI supports native binary, Python, Docker, and WASM workloads. The agent also emits agent events to the manager component.

⁹ SEV Guest - <https://github.com/google/go-sev-guest>

Figure 22. State machine of the agent component waiting for a computation task.

The following figures describe different request and reply classes. These classes are generated using Protocol buffers¹⁰ definitions. Protocol buffers are Google’s language-neutral, platform-neutral, extensible mechanism for serializing structured data that can generate code for different languages.

Figure 23. Data request and response class diagrams.

¹⁰ Protocol buffers - <https://protobuf.dev/>

Figure 24. Attestation request and response class diagrams.

Figure 25. Algorithm request and reply + result request class diagrams.

7.3.2 MANAGER

The manager runs on the TEE-capable host and has two main roles:

- Deploy the well-prepared TEE upon the run command and upload the necessary configuration into it (e.g., command line arguments, TLS certificates)
- Monitor deployed TEE and provide remote logs

The manager also communicates with the Computation Management component. The manager implements the *Service* interface (this has the same name, but this is not the same Service as the interface that the agent implements). The *managerService* contains methods to create and manage confidential virtual machines.

Figure 26. Manager class diagram.

The manager component currently supports AMD SEV-SNP and is using qemu-based method to start confidential virtual machines and vsock-based communications mechanism with the confidential virtual machine. These abstractions need to be generalized to support other platforms as well. The manager also has a state machine with states:

- VmProvision
- VmRunning
- StopComputationRun

Cocos AI virtual machine abstraction is presented in the following picture (Figure 27).

Figure 27. Virtual machine abstraction class diagrams.

7.3.3 CLIENT (CLI)

The client component CLI can be used to perform various tasks related to the computation and management of algorithms, datasets and TEE. The Config struct in Figure 28 shows the structure used for the attestation policy, while the CLI struct shows the CLI options available to the user.

Figure 28. Client class diagram.

7.4 PROCESS VIEW

UML process view deals with the dynamic aspects of the system. Runtime behaviour and interaction of components and main system processes will be explained using, e.g., communications or scenario diagrams.

7.4.1 AGENT

The agent component runs inside the confidential virtual machine. The agent receives a computation manifest that specifies the computing task from the manager and emits agent events that can be used to track the progress of the computing task. The agent component is also fetching an attestation report from the underlying hardware platform (e.g., AMD SEV-SNP). Fetching an attestation report is a hardware platform specific operation. In the case of SEV-SNP, the agent uses the SEV guest driver in the CVM to fetch the attestation report. The operation should be implemented in all supported platforms. Additionally, the agent is a gRPC server for CLI client applications.

Figure 29. The agent component communications diagram.

7.4.2 MANAGER

The manager component is launching a confidential virtual machine and communicates with the virtual machine using vsock. The launch is a platform-specific operation and should be generalized to support multiple platforms. Vsock is a Linux socket family that allows communication between a VM and a hypervisor. It is widely available on multiple platforms.

The manager also communicates with the Computation Management component. A computation manifest that specifies a computing task can be received from the management component. The manager is sending agent events to the Computation Management component so that it can track the computation task. These parts are mostly platform-agnostic code.

Figure 30. Manager communications diagram.

7.5 DEVELOPMENT VIEW

The current Cocos AI implementation is a monorepo that includes all components. The directory structure of the repository is presented in Figure 31.

Figure 31. Source code directory tree.

7.6 PHYSICAL VIEW

Figure 32 describes the locations of the components. There are four different nodes that can be either local computers or computing platforms offered by cloud system providers.

Figure 32. Location of components.

7.7 SCENARIOS

The architecture will be validated using CONFIDENTIAL6G use case 2 (Privacy-preserving confidential computing platform that enables mitigation of internal threats for telecom cloud providers).

7.8 API DEFINITIONS

This document presents only a high-level design and references to the current implementation of Cocos AI [89], which is a starting point to support multiple platforms. The current implementation works with AMD SEV-SNP. More detailed APIs can be defined later to allow porting of Cocos AI to other platforms.

8 CONCLUSION

Confidential computing makes it possible for clients to offload their privacy-sensitive workloads to cloud platforms so that these computing tasks can benefit from the scalability of cloud computing. Confidential virtual machines seem to be a winning concept as the clients can first test their concepts locally and then deploy unmodified workloads to cloud platforms avoiding porting work.

Intel and AMD have been the most popular confidential computing hardware platforms. AMD's confidential virtual machine approach is now followed by Intel and also other platforms like ARM and RISC-V. Earlier approaches had limitations that forced the clients to modify their workloads when utilizing these confidential computing platforms. Although different platforms use different isolation mechanisms to implement confidentiality and integrity protection, the end result from the user's perspective is quite similar. New trends, like edge computing, may create a more heterogeneous computing environment that includes multiple platform architectures. This document presents an analysis of four confidential computing platforms: AMD SEV-SNP, ARM CCA, Intel TDX, and RISC-V CoVE.

While platform providers develop their own confidential computing solutions, the clients are looking for ways to accelerate computing, e.g., for AI/ML workloads. The use of GPUs and even custom FPGA-based accelerators are common ways. From a security point of view, this may bring problems as sensitive data is then processed outside of the protected environment. TDISP specification can be used to include these accelerators in the protected environment.

Remote attestation is a corner-stone of confidential computing architectures. IETF RATS WG specifications have created concepts that are followed by confidential computing architectures.

Because of increasing heterogeneity, there is a need for tools that can hide low-level details from end-users and allow them to easily utilize heterogeneous computing platforms. This document is also analysing a couple of such tools. Many tools support only two platforms. Also plans to further develop the Cocos AI tool to utilize multiple platforms are presented.

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